

Analysis of the decision to use ShopeePay among UPN "Veteran" East Java Students

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Abstract

The goal of this study was to determine how lifestyle, financial literacy, and ease of use affected UPN "Veteran" East Java students' decisions to use ShopeePay. This study uses primary data processing and is quantitative in nature. Data was obtained by survey distribution using G-Form. One hundred UPN "Veteran" East Java students served as the sample, and a non-probability sampling approach was used. The data from the questionnaire will be handled using the Partial Least Square technique and the SmartPLS version 4.0 software. The results of the study show that financial literacy has little bearing on ShopeePay usage. Meanwhile, lifestyle has an impact on ShopeePay usage. Additionally, ShopeePay's ease of use encourages users to use it.

Keywords: Financial Literacy; Lifestyle; Ease of Use; Usage Decision

1. Introduction

Technology is currently developing very rapidly. With this development, it can be utilized in a better direction, supported by a good understanding of how to use it and what risks will occur if you fail to use it. Technological developments occur in all fields. There is no exception in the financial or economic sector. In this field, what is currently developing is digital transactions. This digital transaction is an online payment and sales transaction in an efficient time. This development is usually called financial technology. With the emergence of ShopeePay, it is hoped that generation Z will be able to use it wisely. This generation is used to using technology in their daily activities so that they are comfortable communicating and looking for all the information they need online.

Technology in the financial sector has negative and positive impacts. Therefore, it must be based on financial literacy and an understanding of lifestyle and ease of use. Financial Technology or often referred to as Fintech is a system that combines finance with technology (Purwanto et al, 2022). A number of developments in specialized applications meant for financial sector services have emerged in Indonesia, signaling the rise of financial technology. This can be used as a means of payment transactions, saving money, and can be used as a transaction in borrowing money. This phenomenon can be evidence that there has been a shift in people's habits from a traditional financial system to a financial system using technology. This shift in lifestyle carried out by the Indonesian people is of course directly influenced by the ease and speed of accessing information for the benefit of the community related to the financial system (Ariadin and Safitri, 2021).

The amount of money exchanged electronically in 2019 was IDR 145.1 trillion. While in 2020, its worth climbed to Rp. 204.9 trillion, a 41.2% rise from the previous year. In 2021 it will be IDR. 305.4 trillion, an increase of 49.04%. In 2022 the value of electronic money transactions will reach 399.6 trillion, an increase of 30.84%. In 2023, the value of electronic money transactions will reach 835.84 trillion, an increase of 109.15%. Referring to this significant growth, Bank Indonesia projects Rp. 1,051.24 Trillion in 2024. With the data above, it can be seen that there is a change in people's transaction styles from cash to slowly switching to the use of E- Wallets or electronic money.

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Annual growth in Indonesia's electronic money transaction value has been rather high. In contrast, a poll carried out by the Financial Services Authority (OJK) in 2022 showed that, with a proportion of 49.68%, the general public's level of financial literacy remained low. This percentage increased by 11.65% from 2019. The increase This is not comparable to the sharp increase in the use of electronic money. This can be caused by a person's inability to use a digital wallet system when in a place that only provides a digital payment or cashless payment system. From the results of research on E-Wallet Industry Outlook 2023 ShopeePay. As many as 74% of all respondents have used digital wallets. The digital wallet most used by the public is Gopay while ShopeePay is in fourth place.

The decision to use is a decision that is a choice from several actions carried out through 2 or more alternative choices. According to Ahmad and Iliyini (2019), consumers subconsciously make decisions by making several comparisons of several options that are relevant to what they will use. In analyzing the decision to use ShopeePay in society, especially students, the Acceptance of Technology One theoretical foundation is model theory because this theory is related to a working model which is useful for analyzing how someone can accept and use technology (Wicaksono, 2021). In this research, The elements that impact the choice to using ShopeePay are Financial Literacy, Lifestyle, and also Ease of Use.

Financial literacy is an understanding that humans must have in this modern era, the understanding in question is intelligence in managing the finances of each individual (Alawi et al, 2020). According to the findings of a research by Nurhaeni and Soleha (2023), financial literacy had no influence on Generation Z's desire to use the Go-Pay digital wallet app. In the meanwhile, the findings of a study by Soleha and Hidayah (2022) indicated that financial literacy positively influenced Millennial desire to use the ShopeePay digital wallet.

Lifestyle can explain how a person lives, spends money and uses his time (Prina, 2023). Dewi and Rochmaniah (2023) stated that the use of e-wallets has no influence on the attitudes and lifestyles of the people of Sidoarjo Regency. This contrasts with the findings of a study by Prena and Dewi (2023), which indicated that lifestyle, feeling of security, and trust all significantly positively influence how often people utilize ShopeePay in society.

A person's confidence in resolving current issues is reflected in how easy it is to use technology for transactions (Soleha et al., 2022). According to a research by Mita et al. (2021), consumers' decisions on what to buy on the Shopee marketplace were not influenced by convenience. This contrasts with the findings of Ferdiansyah and Nur's study from 2023, which indicated that the perceived convenience variable was significant. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to examine how financial literacy, lifestyle, and convenience affected UPN "Veteran" East Java students' decisions to utilize ShopeePay.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Theoretical basis

2.1.1. *Technology Acceptance Model*

Fred Davis (1986) in Wicaksono (2021) develops Technology Acceptance Model in his thesis which has the title "A Technology Acceptance Model for Empirically Testing New End Use Information Systems". The Technology Acceptance Model was first created to explain the application of new information system technology by individuals. This theory, according to Pertiwi and Purwanto (2021), is a development and application of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) which focuses on usage modeling. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), according to Wicaksono (2021), is a framework that functions as an understanding of how someone accepts and uses technology.

2.1.2. *Usage Decision*

A usage decision is a decision that is a choice of several actions carried out through 2 or more alternative choices. Unconsciously, consumers make decisions by comparing several relevant choices of goods/services to be consumed (Ahmad and Iliyini 2019). Indicators of usage decisions according to Risma and Dewi (2022) are (1) Product stability (2) Product usage habits or services (3) Providing recommendations to others (4) Reuse.

2.1.3. *Financial Literacy*

A person's ability to obtain, understand, implement, and evaluate information related to their efforts to make decisions by knowing the consequences of their decisions is called financial literacy (Udayanthi, 2018). Financial literacy is the basic knowledge that a person has about finance that must be known and understood by financial practitioners in order to manage their finances so as not to make mistakes in making financial decisions (Pertiwi and Purwanto, 2021). Financial literacy is related to how a person makes personal financial decisions. Financial decision making depends on

awareness, knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors, all of which are components of financial literacy (Nurhaeni and Soleha, 2023). According to Iko (2019), there are 4 indicators in measuring financial literacy, the general understanding of investments, insurance, savings, and loans.

2.1.4. Lifestyle

Laksono and Iskandar (2018), stated that lifestyle is a person's attitude in describing a person's thoughts in various matters related to psychological and emotional problems or can also be seen from what is of interest and what is thought about an object. Al Shabiyah (2019), on the other hand, defines lifestyle as a person's way of living, which includes the items they acquire, how they utilize them, and their thoughts and feelings after doing so. Lifestyle also has to do with how a person responds to the purchases made by customers. According to Nasib, et al. (2021) there are indicators in lifestyle, namely activities, interests and opinions.

2.1.5. Ease of Use

According to Wicaksono (2021), convenience is a person's perception of how easy a technology is to use. The simplicity with which technology may be learned and used, the accessibility of information, and the availability of help all affect how easy something is seen to be.

2.2. Causality and Hypothesis Development

2.2.1. Causality between Financial Literacy and Decision to Use ShopeePay

Financial literacy raises the willingness to make use of financial technology services, as indicated by the results of a research by Pertiwi and Purwanto (2021) that examined the Analysis of the utilize of Financial Technology Services in the Millennial Generation. According to research by Erin Soleha and Zulfa Zakiatul Hidayah (2022), which examined the Impact of Financial Literacy and Transaction Ease on the Millennial Generation's Interest in Using Digital Wallets (ShopeePay), financial literacy positively influences the Millennial Generation's interest in using the ShopeePay digital wallet.

H1: Financial literacy has a positive effect on the decision to use ShopeePay.

2.2.2. Causality between Lifestyle and the decision to use ShopeePay

According to a study by Prena and Dewi (2023), millennial in the city of Denpasar who are interested in utilizing ShopeePay have a favorable effect on their lifestyle. This is consistent with research by Abdillah et al. (2021) that examines the impact of promotion and lifestyle on the decision to use the DANA digital wallet in Karawang Regency. The results show that lifestyle has a major positive effect on the decision to use the DANA digital wallet in the region. Karawang Regency.

H2: Lifestyle has a positive effect on the decision to use ShopeePay.

2.2.3. Causality between ease of use and the decision to use ShopeePay

According to Lusiana and Nur's research findings from 2022, Perceived simplicity of use is a crucial factor that influences students' decisions to use ShopeePay. The convenience variable has a positive impact on DANA e-wallet use, according to a study by Ferdiansyah and Nur (2023), which means that people's decisions to use the DANA e-wallet are mostly impacted by their sense of comfort.

H3: Ease of use has a positive effect on the decision to use ShopeePay.

2.3. Research methods

Quantitative study employing primary data is being conducted here. Through the use of Google Form questionnaires, data was acquired. As the sample for this study, 100 UPN "Veteran" East Java students were given questionnaires. A nonprobability sampling approach was used to select the sampling methodology. The respondents were given a questionnaire with fourteen positive comments that were assessed using a Likert scale with answer choices from Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Disagree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). After obtaining data from respondents, this research utilized partial least squares data analysis tools via the SmartPLS version 4.0 application.

3. Result

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents

	Amount	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Women	69	69%
Man	31	31%
Respondent Basedon Faculty		
Faculty of Economics and Business	22	22%
Faculty of Agriculture	10	10%
Faculty of Engineering	19	19%
Faculty of Social and Political Sciences	23	23%
Faculty of Computer Science	13	13%
Faculty of Architecture and Design	6	6%
Faculty of Law	6	6%
Faculty of Medical	1	1%
Total Respondents	100	

Source of Processed Questionnaire data 2024

The table above indicates that most respondents are female, and that most questionnaires are distributed to the UPN Faculty of Social and Political Sciences "Veteran" East Java. The distribution of each faculty is different due to calculations that are in accordance with the proportion of students in each faculty.

Table 2 Cross Loading

Indicator	Financial Literacy	Lifestyle	Ease of Use	Decision Use
X1. 1	0.854			
X1. 2	0.766			
X1. 3	0.794			
X2. 1		0.827		
X2. 2		0.816		
X2. 3		0.779		
X3. 1			0.765	
X3. 2			0.733	
X3. 3			0.808	
X3. 4			0.735	
Y1. 1				0.783
Y1. 2				0.805
Y1. 3				0.745
Y1. 4				0.766"

Source of Processed Questionnaire data 2024

In this research, the indicators utilized are recognized to have strong validity because in the outer loading results the original sample value was >0.70 with the strongest measure of financial literacy (X1) being general knowledge about personal finance of 0.854. Meanwhile, the strongest lifestyle measure (X2) is opinion at 0.827. Apart from that, the strongest measure of ease of use (X3) is the availability of technical support at 0.808. Finally, the strongest usage decision measure (Y) is product usage habits of 0.805. And the AVE value in this study shows financial literacy (X1) of 0.649, lifestyle (X2) of 0.652, ease of use (X3) of 0.579, and decision to use (Y) of 0.601. So the convergent validity test in this research has been declared valid. Furthermore, in testing discriminant validity in understanding the extent to which the variable being studied is different from other variables. This process involves cross loading analysis which indicates that the factor loading of the indicators in this study more strongly connected to the variable than to the factor loading of other variables. The results show that the discriminant validity criteria in this study have been met.

Meanwhile, in the reliability testing stage, this research uses the results of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability study. The composite reliability analysis's findings demonstrate that the value of financial literacy (X1) is 0.847, lifestyle (X2) is 0.849, ease of use (X3) is 0.846 and decision to use (Y) is 0.857. Meanwhile, Cronbach's alpha values indicate that the organizational culture value (X1) obtained a financial literacy value (X1) of 0.735, lifestyle (X2) of 0.732, ease of use (X3) of 0.757 and decision to use (Y) of 0.779. The two tests' findings indicate a value of >0.70, which means that the indicators from the research instrument are consistent and reliable for measuring the same variable.

Figure 1 PLS Bootstrapping Model

Meanwhile, testing the inner model can be done through statistical significance tests, adjusted R square, and Q square values. Statistical significance testing involves analysis of latent variables correlations with a focus on the highest correlation value between variables. In the test results in this study, The relationship between the factors' ease of use (X3) and lifestyle (X2) shows the strongest correlation compared to the correlation between other variables. The correlation between these two variables reached 0.665.

Table 3 R- Square

	R-square Adjusted
Usage Decisions	0.497

SmartPLS Data Processing Result, 2024

In this research, it is known thus the R square corrected value is 0.497, indicating that there is an influence of 49.7% from financial literacy (X1), lifestyle (X2), ease of use (X3), and decision to use (Y). Meanwhile, factors not included in this study have an impact on the remaining 51.1%.

Table 4 Path Coefficients(Mean, STDEV, T-Values)

	Path Coefficient	P values	Information
Literacy Finance (X1) -> Usage Decision (Y)	0.116	0.132	Non. Significant
Lifestyle (X2) -> Usage Decisions (Y)	0.368	0,000	Significant
Ease of Use (X3) -> Use Decision (Y)	0.364	0.001	Significant

SmartPLS Data Processing Result, 2024

At the test stage using partial least squares, hypothesis testing is needed through the results of estimating path coefficients through bootstrapping. It is known that H1, financial literacy has no influence on the decision to use ShopeePay, is rejected. The positive Path Coefficient value of 0.116 and the P Values of 0.132 > 0.005 provide evidence of these outcomes. Furthermore, H2, which shows that lifestyle influences ShopeePay decisions favorably, is admissible. Based on a positive Path Coefficient value of 0.368 and a P value of 0.000 < 0.05, these findings are presented. Finally, H3—ease of use—can be accepted and has a favorable impact on the choice to utilize ShopeePay. Based on a positive path coefficient value of 0.364 and a P value of 0.001 < 0.05, these findings are presented.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Influence of Financial Literacy on Decisions to Use ShopeePay

Hypothesis (H1) states that financial literacy contributes positively to the decision to use ShopeePay. Based on the data analysis carried out, the result was that financial literacy on the decision to use ShopeePay had no contribution so it was rejected. This means that financial literacy does not influence the decision to use ShopeePay among UPN "Veteran" East Java students. This can be seen as the P Values for this variable are above 0.05. The general knowledge indication about personal finance has the largest factor loading in this variable. This suggests that in addition to being influenced by information acquisition, implementation and assessment must also increase a person's incentive to use Shoepeepay. When someone only understands but doesn't use ShopeePay, this is in vain. Basically financial literacy is a must has the factors of understanding, implementing and evaluating. Apart from financial literacy, a person's decision to use ShopeePay can be influenced by digital literacy. Because it can make it easier to understand how to easily use the features provided by ShopeePay. If someone only has high financial literacy but it is not balanced with high digital literacy, someone will not feel the ease of using a digital wallet which results in reluctance to use it.

The results of this investigation are reliable with earlier research by Ferdiansyah and Nur (2023), which found no relationship between financial literacy and the choice to use the DANA e-wallet. This study details how students at UPN "Veteran" East Java's economics and business faculties spend their e-wallet funds. This is similar to the topic being researched, namely conducting research on the decision to use e-wallets which are currently developing in Indonesia. Similar research conducted by Nuhaeni and Soleha (2023) said that there was no impact from financial literacy on interest in using the Go-Pay digital wallet application.

However, The findings of this study conflict with those of Lusiana and Nur (2022) investigation which states that financial literacy contributes to increasing students' decisions to use ShopeePay.

4.2. The Influence of Lifestyle on Decisions to Use ShopeePay

The study's findings indicate that a person's lifestyle has a favorable and substantial impact on their decision to utilize ShopeePay. It can be interpreted that a person's lifestyle greatly influences a person's desires in deciding to use ShopeePay. In this variable, the indicator with the highest factor loading is the opinion indicator. Someone's opinion about something can lead someone to do it. It can be stated that when someone with a modern lifestyle has the opinion that using ShopeePay can make it easier for them to carry out daily transactions, of course their desire to use ShopeePay will be very high. In addition, someone's opinion about the security of an application can influence someone's use of it. If someone believes that ShopeePay is a digital wallet that has good security then this will encourage someone to use it.

Apart from opinions, the decision to use ShopeePay can be influenced by their interests and the activities they carry out daily.

The results of this investigation are reliable with earlier research by Dewi and Prena (2023), which found that lifestyle significantly and favorably influences interest in usage. The findings of related studies carried out by Andana and Yuniningsih (2023).

4.3. The Influence of Ease of Use on Decisions to Use ShopeePay

The results of the survey show that simplicity of usage has a noteworthy and favorable impact on people's choices to utilize ShopeePay. It is possible to draw the conclusion that ShopeePay's ease of use has a big impact on people's decisions to use it. The indication of product consumption habits has the largest factor loading in this variable. This implies that a person's interest in using ShopeePay will increase as they become more accustomed to using it for everyday transactions. People who use ShopeePay as a transaction instrument in the same setting typically have an impact on this usage behavior. And this habit could also be influenced by the promotions offered by ShopeePay so that it can attract someone's attention to use it continuously. Apart from habitual use of the product, the decision to use a digital wallet can also be influenced by security, product capabilities related to the facilities provided, and also recommendations from people around the user.

The results of this investigation are reliable with those of Ferdiansyah and Nur's (2023) research, which found that perceived convenience positively influenced users' decisions to use the DANA e-wallet. In addition, comparable findings from the research of Lusiana and Nur (2022) were also achieved.

5. Conclusion

This research examines Financial Literacy, Lifestyle, The Decision to Use ShopeePay: Its User-Friendliness among UPN "Veteran" East Java Students. The following conclusions may be drawn from research that indicates financial literacy does not really influence people's decisions to utilize ShopeePay, based on the findings of that research as well as discussions of earlier findings. This is due to the fact that having financial literacy requires more than just comprehension; it also requires execution and assessment. It is therefore possible to gauge the choice to utilize ShopeePay using factors other than financial literacy. According to the study's findings, a person's lifestyle definitely influences whether or not they choose to utilize ShopeePay. This is a result of students adopting ShopeePay due to their modern lifestyle. Convenience and security opinions may be taken into account while making a decision. Convenience of use has a substantial impact on ShopeePay usage, according to the results of the completed study. This is due to the ease of the application offered by ShopeePay so that it can increase students' interest in using it. The suggestion that can be drawn from this research is that this modern lifestyle can be used in a better direction in developing technology in the financial sector so that it can be more useful. Apart from that, the ease of use of an application must be maintained by each application in order to keep people using it. Lastly, further research can use other variables outside this research such as self-control variables or usage experience and can enlarge the study object so that the findings of additional research can represent the general public.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Andana, RR, & Yuniningsih, Y. (2023). Financial Management Behavior in Using Fintech (Study on Management Students of UPN Veteran East Java). *Journal of Accounting Finance and Auditing Studies (JAFAS)*. <https://doi.org/10.32602/jafas.2023.024> Ariadin,
- [2] M., & Safitri, TA (2021). Financial Management Behavior in Central MSMEs Wooden Crafts in Dompu Regency. *Journal Among Makarti*, 14, 31. Ferdiansyah, MR, & Nur, DI (2023). Factors Affecting Decision to Use DANA E-Wallet
- [3] for Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business UPN “Veteran” East Java. *Management Studies and Entrepreneurship Journal*, 4, 7970–7978.
- [4] Iko Putri Yanti, W. (2019). The Influence of Financial Inclusion and Financial Literacy on MSME Performance in North Moyo District. *Journal of Management and Business*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.37673/jmb.v2i1.305>
- [5] Iliyini, A., & Widiartanto, W. (2019). The Influence of Perceived Ease of Use And Security Perceptions of the Decision to Use Ovo Pt Visionet Data Internasional (Study of Ovo Users in Surakarta City). *Journal of Business Administration*, 9(1), 85–92. <https://doi.org/10.14710/jiab.2020.26225>
- [6] “Boku Report: OVO Leads Mobile Wallet Market Share in Indonesia | DailySocial.id.” *Dailysocial*, 13 July 2021, <https://dailysocial.id/post/report-boku-ovo-pimpin-pangsapasar-mobile-wallet-di-indonesia>. Accessed 7 May 2024.
- [7] Lusiana, A., Ichsanuddin, D., Key Abstract Keywords, K., Finance, L., Services, K., Ease of Use, P., & Finance, P. (2022). Usage Decision Analysis ShopeePay Management Student of East Java “Veteran” National Development University. *Journal of Social Economics and Humanities*, 8, 391–397.
- [8] Mita, Pranatasari, FD, & Kristia. (2021). Analysis of the Effect of Price, Ease of Use, and Consumer Reviews of Purchasing Decisions on the Shopee Marketplace. *Indonesian Journal of Business Innovation and Management*, Vol. 4(4), 548–557.
- [9] Fate, Tambunan, D., & Syaifullah. (2021). *Consumer Behavior (Studies in Selection College)* (M. Hasan, Ed.; Print 1). Nuta Media.
- [10] Pertiwi, TK, & Purwanto, E. (2021). Analysis of Adopting Millennial Generation Financial Technology (Fintech) Services. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 04(03). <https://doi.org/10.35409/ijbmer.2021.3257>
- [11] Prena, G. Das, & Dewi, NKSG (2023b). Influence of Ease of Use, Lifestyle, Perception of Security and Trust in Interest in Using ShopeePay. *ECONOMIC DISCOURSE (Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting)*, 22(2), 142–155. <https://doi.org/10.22225/we.22.2.2023.142-155>
- [12] Rania, D. (2024, April 5). Most Favorite Digital Wallet Survey in Indonesia (2024). *Jubelio*. Soleha, E., & Zulfa
- [13] Zakiatul Hidayah. (2022). The Effect of Financial Literacy and Convenience Transactions on the Millennial Generation's Interest in Using Digital Wallets (ShopeePay). *ARBITRATION: Journal of Economics and Accounting*, 3(2), 312–316. <https://doi.org/10.47065/arbitrage.v3i2.505>
- [14] Suriani, S. (2022). *Financial Behavior* (Suginam & VW Sari, Eds.; Print 1). Foundation WE Write.
- [15] Wicaksono, SR (2022). *Basic Theory of Technology Acceptance Model*. Malang: CV. One thousand Star.